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PUBLIC PROCUREMENT EFFICIENCY DURING WARTIME: MECHANISMS FOR OPTIMIZING BUDGET EXPENDITURE

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Abstract. The article explores the features of public procurement within the public finance system of Ukraine. It analyzes the specific characteristics of public procurement practices in Ukraine and their alignment with EU requirements, as well as the factors influencing their effectiveness. The study examines the challenges faced by Ukraine in conducting tenders during wartime and identifies ways to overcome deficiencies in public procurement under current conditions.

Following Russia's invasion of Ukraine in 2022, the country suffered substantial economic losses, necessitating significant budget savings. The 2022 budget was executed largely thanks to support from international partners, although many procurement processes were canceled due to the reallocation of funds for the purchase of weapons and military equipment. The issue of increasing the efficiency of public spending, particularly through improving tender procedures to minimize corruption, became more pressing than ever. In 2023, the situation with budget execution partially improved, allowing broader use of tender procedures, especially for the procurement of food and supplies for security forces. However, the level of corruption in these processes remained largely unchanged. This highlights the urgent need for reform of procurement legislation and improvements in the performance of public oversight institutions. Moreover, it is vital to strengthen public involvement in procurement processes at all levels, including for defense needs. The practice of 2022 showed that when public procurement bypassed the Prozorro system, prices for many goods, works, and services rose sharply compared to free market prices. This was particularly evident in the procurements by entities under the Ministry of Defense of Ukraine, which were often labeled as "classified." Under pressure from civil society and international donors, the Ukrainian government was forced to partially open the Ministry's procurement system to the public. However, this has not yet led to a significant improvement in efficiency. Therefore, the next step must involve a comprehensive revision of procurement legislation and maximum transparency of procurement data. Without such measures, Ukraine will not be able to attract substantial foreign investment for post-war reconstruction.

Keywords: public procurement, budget funds, Prozorro system, tender procedure, corruption, financing strategy, financial management, martial law.

Анотація. В статті розкрито особливості публічних закупівель в системі публічних фінансів України; проаналізовані особливості здійснення публічних закупівель в Україні та їх відповідність вимогам ЄС, а також чинники, які впливають на їх ефективність; досліджені проблеми, які існують в Україні при проведенні тендерних закупівель в умовах

воєнного часу; виявлено шляхи подолання недоліків у проведенні публічних закупівель в сучасних умовах.

В умовах вторгнення Росії в Україну в 2022 р. наша країна зазнала значних економічних втрат, що вимагає суттєвої економії бюджетних витрат. Бюджет 2022 року вдалося виконати завдячуючи допомозі зарубіжних партнерів, але багато закупівель були відмінені через перенаправлення коштів на закупівлю озброєння та військової техніки. Як ніколи гостро постало питання підвищення ефективності використання бюджетних коштів, в тому числі через удосконалення тендерних закупівель щоб мінімізувати корупцію при їх проведенні. У 2023 р. ситуація у використанні бюджетних коштів частково покращилася, що дало можливість ширше використовувати тендерні закупівлі, зокрема, при закупівлях продуктів харчування та речового майна для силових структур. Водночас, рівень корупції при їх здійсненні суттєво не зменшився. Це вимагає значного реформування тендерного законодавства та покращення роботи державних контролюючих структур. Крім того, важливо посилити роль громадськості при проведенні публічних закупівель на всіх рівнях, в тому числі й для потреб оборони. Практика їх проведення в 2022 р. показала, як тільки публічні закупівлі пішли в обхід системи Prozorro, ціни на багато товарів, робіт і послуг різко зросли у порівнянні з цінами на вільному ринку. Насамперед, це проявилось при проведенні закупівель товарів і послуг з боку відповідних структур Міністерства оборони України, які прикривалися грифом «таємно». Під тиском громадськості та міжнародних спонсорів українська влада була змушена частково розкрити систему публічних закупівель в цьому Міністерстві, але суттєвого підвищення їх ефективності поки не вдалося досягти. Тому наступним кроком повинен стати суттєвий перегляд тендерного законодавства та максимального відкриття матеріалів публічних закупівель для громадськості. Інакше Україна не зможе отримати значні закордонні інвестиції для відбудови країни після війни.

Ключові слова: публічні закупівлі, бюджетні кошти, система Prozorro, тендерна процедура, корупція, стратегія фінансування, фінансове управління, воєнний стан.

Introduction

Problem Statement. Changes in the public finance system of Ukraine in the last decade are characterized primarily by a decrease in the role of the state and an increase in the role of local governments in the functioning of the public sector of our country's economy. Despite the war, the volume of public procurement today is gradually approaching the level of 2021, although certain types of defense-related procurement are not always used in a legal manner. Therefore, one of the main tasks of reforming the public finance sector in our country is to implement an effective mechanism for using public procurement in accordance with the principles and approaches used by EU countries, since Ukraine has received the status of a candidate for accession to the European Union. It is also important to coordinate the process of localization of production of certain goods in Ukraine with the requirements of the EU so as not to violate the requirements of this organization. In addition, the Ukrainian authorities need to accelerate the application of "green" public procurement, which will allow our country to adequately respond to the requirements of the European Green Deal. In addition, the Ukrainian authorities should strive to minimize corruption in public procurement (especially in the defense sector) in order to improve the situation in the field of public finances. Especially since Ukraine's partner countries constantly emphasize this.

The latter are ready to allocate significant financial resources for the reconstruction of our country, but under the control of their representatives. Accordingly, Ukrainian legislators need to make significant changes to the mechanism of public procurement in order to attract funds from various international structures and individual countries to their implementation, which will significantly expand the financial base for public procurement in modern conditions. So far, such issues are not even discussed, which may

negatively affect the volume of public finances of our country, which are directed to the reconstruction of Ukraine.

Analysis of Recent Research and Publications. Today, more and more foreign and Ukrainian scientists and practitioners are looking for new approaches to solving the problems of increasing the efficiency of public finances and directing them to achieving sustainable development standards. Russia's war against Ukraine and its negative consequences for the functioning of public finances and the environment require the search for adequate solutions to solve this new problem for the world community and our country, which has suffered the most from this war. According to the Prime Minister of Ukraine D. Shmyhal, as of early August 2023, only supporting the Armed Forces of Ukraine and the war cost our country about UAH 2 trillion per year. This is more than the revenue part of the peacetime budget, which amounted to UAH 1.3 trillion. In addition, our country has lost 3.5 million jobs and about 30% of the Ukrainian economy [1]. According to forecasts, Ukraine's public debt in 2024 and the following years will rapidly approach the level of 100% of the country's GDP. Only financial support from democratic countries, international financial organizations and charitable foundations gives hope that Ukraine will receive the necessary financial resources to repel Russian aggression. At the same time, the projected decrease in foreign financial support to Ukraine in 2024 puts on the agenda the maximum optimization of public finances, including through improving public procurement. One of the ways to increase the efficiency of public finances can be to improve public procurement in Ukraine, taking into account the experience of democratic countries on this issue. A number of foreign and Ukrainian scientists have made a significant contribution to the development of theoretical and practical problems of public finance. In particular, a significant contribution to the development of public finance issues was made by such foreign scientists as: A. Smith, D. Ricardo, A. Pigou, K. Wicksel, A. Lerner, A. Downs, D. Stiglitz, S. Blanchard, J. M. Buchanan, R. Musgrave, A. Wagner, V. Humboldt, A. Pareto, E. Lindahl, G. Tullock, A. Marshall. A significant contribution to the development of the theory of state and public finance was made by such well-known Ukrainian scientists as V. Andrushchenko, O. Vasylyk, G. Voloshchuk, T. I. Yefymenko, O. P. Kyrylenko, V. Kravchenko, A. Krysovaty, M. Krupka, I. Lunina, I. Lyuty, P. Nikiforov, Ts. Ogon, V. Oparin, K. Pavlyuk, Yu. Pasichnyk, I. Rozputenko, S. Slukhai, V. Fedosov, I. Chugunov, S. Yuriy and others.

The theoretical and methodological foundations of the use of public procurement in countries around the world and in Ukraine were studied by such foreign and Ukrainian scientists as: G. Azarenkova, M. Bilukha, I. Bondar, A. Boyer, A. Brandon-Jones, O. Vorobyowa, V. Geyets, V. Horyn, A. Davil, O. Dlugopolsky, T. Zhyber, O. Mishchenko, T. Moroz, V. Morozov, O. Ovsyanyuk-Berladina, D. Kaufman, J. Matechak, A. Olefir, N. Panayotou, O. Ryzhova, I. Sydorenko, N. Tkachenko, G. Kharchenko, A. Heineman, V. Chaban, I. Chorna, R. Shapper, O. Shatkovsky. At the same time, an in-depth analysis of the experience of conducting public procurement in Ukraine shows that our country still has enough problems in this area, in particular, those related to the implementation of "green" procurement, as well as when conducting public procurement during the war.

Purpose of the Article. The purpose and objectives of the study. All of the above indicates the need to identify ways to increase the efficiency of taxpayers' money and maximize the optimization of budget expenditures (including public procurement), despite external investments. In accordance with the stated goal, it is important to solve the following tasks: to investigate ways to achieve maximum efficiency in conducting public procurement, to analyze each of the stages of their conduct and preparation of tender documentation, to introduce an initiative to amend the legislation and adapt it to EU norms, to develop a strategy for financing public expenditures that will take into account the peculiarities of martial law in Ukraine. This strategy should determine the priorities of expenditures, as well as sources of financing, such as attracting external loans, mobilizing internal resources and effective use of existing budget funds, and allocating priority expenditures under martial law. These may be the costs of providing.

Results

The introduction of martial law in Ukraine has led to significant changes in the regulatory framework governing public procurement. In particular, certain norms of the Law of Ukraine "On Public Procurement" have been suspended, and new mechanisms for procurement under martial law have been introduced by the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine. This includes simplified procurement procedures, centralized procurement through designated authorities, and increased discretionary powers for procuring entities in emergency situations.

The state in the conditions of formation and development of a market economy is one of the main participants in the economic process not only from the point of view of its performance of control and regulation functions, but also from the point of view of the fact that it acts as a fairly powerful consumer of goods, works and services. For the most part, this problem is solved by acquiring the necessary resources through public procurement. Therefore, it is important to achieve effective use of budget funds allocated for public procurement in Ukraine, which has not yet been achieved. In addition, it is necessary to identify ways to improve the implementation of public procurement in wartime, while preventing Russia from obtaining information about certain types of defense procurement.

In recent years, more and more Ukrainian scientists and practitioners have been looking for new approaches to solving the problems of increasing the financial efficiency of Ukraine's public finances, since defense spending and the size of the state debt are growing at a significant pace.

Therefore, it is important to use public finances more effectively, in particular for public procurement, including in the defense sector, where significant losses of budget funds are still occurring. Accordingly, increasing transparency in the use of public finances at all levels of government is an important change in them, which has a positive impact on their volumes.

Despite Russia's war against Ukraine, the Ukrainian authorities are gradually increasing the openness of defense procurement, which should increase their efficiency. The volumes of public procurement through the Prozorro electronic system, which were significantly reduced at the beginning of the war, are also increasing. If in 2021 these volumes amounted to about 1 trillion UAH, then in 2022 they decreased to 160 billion UAH, and in 2023 their volume increased to 480 billion UAH. In addition, from 09/28/2023, the sale and lease of assets of state joint-stock companies takes place through online auctions in the Prozorro electronic system. Sales. In general, in 2023, 14 billion UAH was received by budgets of different levels thanks to bidding in this system [2]. According to the results of the auctions, the starting price for assets doubled, and almost 26 thousand participants took part in the auctions. They bought and rented state and municipal real estate, land at online auctions, received special permits for the use of subsoil, for fishing in a transparent manner, competed for the assets of bankrupts, including the assets of bankrupt banks. In total, in 2023 in the Prozorro system. Sales were sold by more than 3.5 thousand organizers at state online auctions.

The efficiency of public bidding was positively affected by the state's requirement to the State Property Fund of Ukraine to sell public property (state and municipal) with small-scale privatization at online auctions in the Prozorro system. Sales. According to their results, the state budget received more than 2.6 billion UAH in 2023. Privatization of municipal property brought more than 650 million UAH to territorial communities. According to the results of such electronic auctions, the price of objects put up for privatization increased almost threefold.

Among territorial communities, the city of Dnipro worked best with the small privatization market - 35 successful auctions, Lviv - 32 auctions and Kyiv - 23 auctions [3]. An important condition for increasing the efficiency of public finances through public procurement may be the expansion of the participation of centralized purchasing organizations (CPOs) in this process, the number of which in our country is gradually increasing. In the EU, the history of centralized purchasing goes back decades, and CPOs are the most influential part of the public procurement sphere, through which tens of billions of euros are purchased annually. In contrast, in Ukraine, purchases by central purchasing organizations account for less than 1% of their total number, which are carried out by 4 CPOs at the central level and 7 at the regional level [4]. All mandatory centralized purchases in the interests of central executive bodies were suspended at the end of February 2022. due to the war and were restored only in June 2023, which complicates the analysis of their

effectiveness. Nevertheless, based on a study by the State Enterprise "Professional Procurement" of public procurement of electricity, it turned out that decentralized procurement is on average almost 11% more expensive than centralized procurement of electricity. Therefore, we can conclude that the number of CPOs in our country should increase if the state wants to achieve higher efficiency of public procurement. Obtaining the status of a candidate for accession to the European Union by Ukraine requires an expansion of the number of centralized procurement organizations not only at the central level, but also at the local level.

Thus, in EU countries, CPOs can operate at different levels of government: national, regional, local. One of the financial advantages of creating centralized purchasing organizations is the reduction of costs for both the public sector and business for conducting the procurement itself, which is characterized by fewer procedures and fewer people involved, and significant time savings for their implementation [5].

A significant financial effect for increasing the efficiency of public finances in Ukraine can be achieved by improving them at leading state-owned enterprises that carry out public procurement for hundreds of millions of UAH. This is evidenced, in particular, by the reorganization of these procurements in 2018-2023 at NPC Ukrenergo, which resulted in significant savings of public funds [6]. This was also facilitated by the fact that NPC Ukrenergo, one of the first Ukrainian state-owned companies, transferred all procurement to the Prozorro platform, created the institute of authorized persons responsible for public procurement, the supply chain management directorate, and introduced auxiliary functions of internal audit and compliance. As a result, public procurement at this enterprise became more transparent and competitive. It also created safeguards against corruption and fraud, changed approaches to the formation of technical tasks and setting a fair price, and established the responsibility of counterparties for poor-quality and untimely fulfillment of obligations.

All this was achieved through such basic actions that are important to apply to defense enterprises, which quite often conduct these auctions with significant violations. 1. For the transparency of public procurement, the technical task must be discussed with market participants, which will make it possible to attract the maximum number of participants to the auction. 2. Strict price control, which will ensure proper protection of contracts. 3. Sanctions against bidders must be enforced, which will reduce unjustified disruption of tenders. 4. All advances from the customer must be protected by a bank guarantee. 5. Everything that can be digitized must be digitized. 6. People who are to work in public procurement must share the following common values: openness, transparency, innovation and professionalism. The result of these actions was that during Ukrenergo tenders, the price for goods, works and services for it was reduced by 10-15% from the previously proposed one. Thanks to this, over the past 5 years, the company has saved more than UAH 1.2 billion on public procurement, and more than 2 companies have applied for each tender. The legislative requirement to improve the submission of complaints about the results of public procurement in electronic form is an important condition for increasing the efficiency of using public finances in Ukraine. Accordingly, in the near future, the electronic trading platform Prozorro will update the functionality for submitting electronic complaints to the Antimonopoly Committee of Ukraine (AMCU), which will be submitted in the form of an electronic document. Additional fields have been added to it for complainants to fill in the complaint. Tips and instructions will help fill in the new fields, which will allow them to correctly state the content of the complaint. In addition, when working with the classifier of the essence of the objections in the complaint, it is necessary to choose values that correspond as closely as possible to the essence of the complaint. The AMCU recommends that complainants fill in the fields of the electronic document of the complaint as correctly as possible, since failure to comply with this form will be grounds for its rejection. However, the specified norm will come into force after the end of martial law. In Ukraine, it should be taken into account that in the EU, solving the problem of increasing the environmental friendliness of public procurement has significantly accelerated the implementation of the so-called "green procurement", although their price is higher compared to traditional procurement. The European

Commission defines "green procurement" as a process during which customers purchase goods, works and services with a limited impact on the environment throughout their entire life cycle compared to goods,

works and services of the same functional purpose [7]. Among the types of goods most actively promoted within the concept of “green” procurement in the EU are the following: energy-efficient appliances; office furniture made from environmentally friendly materials; paper made from recycled materials; electric cars; electricity obtained from renewable sources [8]. At the same time, it should be remembered that, according to estimates by authoritative international experts, by 2030, the implementation of “green” projects in the world will require additional financing in the amount of 90 trillion US dollars, which will make it difficult for Ukraine to obtain such funds during wartime and reconstruction [9].

Public-private partnership in Ukraine is now significantly expanding the range of its subjects. Today, they are international organizations, charitable organizations of democratic countries, famous foreign artists, athletes, politicians, etc., who use their own funds to finance the reconstruction of housing by private structures for the most affected Ukrainian citizens, educational and healthcare institutions, etc. It is also noteworthy that similar funds are invested by philanthropists in the processing of construction waste, which is then used as secondary raw materials in the construction of housing and roads. In this regard, an illustrative example is the reconstruction of housing by a French construction company in the city of Gostomel, Kyiv region, the work of which was financed by French charitable organizations under the control of Ukrainian state and local authorities [10]. However, it should be taken into account that foreign sponsors are still afraid to allocate significant financial resources to Ukrainian state structures to finance such work through public procurement, since they are deterred by significant corruption in these bodies. Therefore, all projects for the reconstruction of Ukraine, for which the world community is ready to allocate hundreds of billions of dollars over the next 10 years, will be considered by their representatives, and then implemented by private structures from Ukraine and foreign countries. It is important that part of these funds go through public procurement by Ukrainian customers of works with the financial participation of foreign investors [11].

Conclusions

One of the main tasks of reforming the public finance sector in our country is to implement an effective mechanism for using public procurement in accordance with the principles applied by EU countries, since Ukraine has received the status of a candidate for accession to this organization. This task is complicated by the fact that a significant part of public procurement in the context of Russia's war against our country is classified and quite often they are not effective enough.

The Ukrainian authorities should not only significantly increase the efficiency of public procurement and its justification, but also strive to minimize corruption during these procurements (especially in the defense sector) in order to improve the situation in the field of public finances. Especially since this is constantly emphasized by Ukraine's partner countries, which are ready to allocate significant financial resources for the reconstruction of our country.

The main goal of financial management under martial law in Ukraine is the effective use of budget funds to ensure national security, defense, and respond to economic challenges that arise during this period. To do this, it is necessary to solve several tasks that need to be solved to achieve this goal. First of all, it is necessary to develop an appropriate financing strategy and properly reform the legislation on public procurement. During the war between Russia and Ukraine, changes in the legislation simplified participation in procurement and ensured efficiency in decision-making and purchasing what is necessary, primarily for defense needs. At the same time, as evidenced by publications in the media by independent experts, the general public is faced with the fact of concealment of information and weakening of control by state regulatory bodies over large-scale procurements worth hundreds of billions of hryvnias, which could have been stolen from the defense budget.

This model of procurement management leads to low efficiency in public procurement and generates even greater corruption risks than those present before the war. Accordingly, there is a pressing need to address this issue by developing an effective model for managing both state and externally sourced funds, including aid and loans. One possible solution could involve the inclusion of representatives from independent civil society organizations in the oversight of defense procurements.

This procurement model leads to low efficiency of public procurement and generates even more corruption risks than the pre-war one. Therefore, it is worth working on solving this problem and developing an effective model for managing state and attracted funds in the form of aid or loans. One of the options for solving this problem could be to involve representatives of independent public structures in the control of defense procurement. Ukraine needs to more widely apply the experience of EU countries, primarily the Visegrad Group countries, in conducting public procurement at all levels and organizing appropriate control over them. In particular, it is proposed to adopt the experience of Poland in implementing a financial control mechanism with appropriate punitive measures, which will lead to minimizing corruption risks in Ukraine, including during wartime.

Ukraine must also more broadly adopt the experience of EU countries, particularly the Visegrád Group (Poland, Hungary, Czech Republic, and Slovakia), in organizing public procurement across all levels and implementing appropriate control mechanisms. In particular, it is recommended to follow Poland's example of introducing a financial control mechanism accompanied by enforceable sanctions. Such measures would significantly reduce corruption risks in Ukraine, including under the ongoing conditions of martial law. [12]

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